

Effect of Freezing and Boiling Treatments on Seed Germination

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Abstract

Germination is the process by which a seed grows into a new plant. Temperature plays an important role in this process. In this study, the effect of freezing and boiling on wheat seed germination was observed. Wheat seeds (*Triticum aestivum*) were divided into three groups: untreated seeds (control), seeds frozen in water for about 25 hours at 0 to -20 °C, and seeds boiled in water for 10 minutes. All seeds were planted under the same conditions and observed daily for 20 days. All control seeds germinated, only some frozen seeds germinated, and no boiled seeds germinated. The results show that freezing reduces germination but does not completely stop it, while boiling completely prevents germination.

Keywords: seed germination, wheat, freezing, boiling, temperature effect

Introduction

Seeds need suitable conditions such as water, oxygen, and proper temperature to germinate. Temperature is one of the most important factors that affects seed growth. Very high or very low temperatures can damage seeds and stop them from growing.

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) is an important food crop and is commonly used in plant studies because it germinates easily under normal conditions. This study was done to understand how extreme temperatures, such as freezing and boiling, affect the germination of wheat seeds.

Objective

The objective of this study was to observe the effect of freezing and boiling on the germination of wheat seeds (*Triticum aestivum*).

Method

Materials

Wheat seeds (*Triticum aestivum*)

Natural soil

Three ceramic cups

Water

Freezer

Heating source for boiling

Experimental Design

The experiment included three groups, with five seeds in each group:

Control group: Seeds with no treatment.

Frozen group: Seeds placed in water and frozen at approximately 0 to -20°C for about 25 hours. After freezing, seeds were allowed to thaw naturally and then planted.

Boiled group: Seeds boiled in water for 10 minutes, removed, cooled, and then planted.

Planting and Conditions

All seeds were planted on 12.12.2025 in ceramic cups filled with the same soil. Seeds were planted on the soil surface at a depth of about 0–0.1 cm. All cups were kept together in the same room.

Room temperature ranged from 10 °C to 30 °C. Light was provided by a dim LED source. No direct sunlight was used.

Watering and Observation

All cups were watered in the same way. Watering details were recorded and are attached as a data sheet at the end of the paper. Germination was checked and recorded daily from 12.12.2025 to 31.12.2025.

A seed was considered germinated when the seedling was visible above the soil surface.

Results

The results of the experiment were as follows:

Control group: 5 out of 5 seeds germinated (100%).

Frozen group[FREEZED]: 2 out of 5 seeds germinated (40%).

Boiled group[BOILED]: 0 out of 5 seeds germinated (0%).

These results show that freezing reduced the number of seeds that germinated, while boiling completely stopped germination.

Discussion

All control seeds germinated, showing that the soil, water, and environmental conditions were suitable for wheat seed growth. Some frozen seeds were able to germinate, which means freezing did not kill all seeds. However, freezing reduced germination, likely due to damage caused by ice formation inside the seeds.

No seeds germinated after boiling.

Limitations

Only five seeds were used in each group.

The experiment was performed only once.

Temperature was not controlled using laboratory equipment.

Conclusion

This study shows that extreme temperatures affect wheat seed germination. Freezing seeds in water for about 25 hours reduced germination but did not completely stop it. Boiling seeds for 10 minutes completely prevented germination. These results help in understanding how temperature stress affects seed growth.

References

No external references were used. This study is based on direct observation and experimentation.

(All raw data are attached at the end of the paper.)

" Data is in cm "

PLANT GROWTH DATA

DATE	NSP	FSP	BSP
11.12.2025	0	0	0
12.12.2025	0	0	0
13.12.2025	0	0	0
14.12.2025	0	0	0
15.12.2025	0	0	0
16.12.2025	SG	SG	0
17.12.2025	G	G	0
18.12.2025	G	G	0
19.12.2025	2	2.2	0
20.12.2025	3.2	4.3	0
21.12.2025	7	7.1	0
22.12.2025	8.8	9.8	0
23.12.2025	12.2	12.7	0
24.12.2025	14.5	15	0
25.12.2025	16	17.5	0
26.12.2025	17.8	18.7	0
27.12.2025	20.2	19.2	0
28.12.2025	21	19.2	0
29.12.2025	21	19.2	0
30.12.2025	21.2	19.2	0
31.12.2025	22.7	19.2	0
NSP=Natural Seed growing Process			
FSP=Freezed Seed growing Process			
BSP=Boiled Seed growing Process			
SG=Started Growing			
G=Growing			

WATER DATA

DATE	NSP	FSP	BSP
11.12.2025			
12.12.2025			
13.12.2025			
14.12.2025			
15.12.2025			
16.12.2025			
17.12.2025			
18.12.2025			
19.12.2025			
20.12.2025			
21.12.2025			
22.12.2025			
23.12.2025			
24.12.2025			
25.12.2025			
26.12.2025			
27.12.2025			
28.12.2025			
29.12.2025			
30.12.2025			
31.12.2025			

	In Processing
	Water given
	Water Not given

GROWTH DATA					
NSP					
DATE	1	2	3	4	5
11.12.2025	-	-	-	-	-
12.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
13.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
14.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
15.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
16.12.2025	SG	SG	0	0	0
17.12.2025	G	G	SG	0	0
18.12.2025	G	G	G	SG	0
19.12.2025	2	1.3	0.4	0.2	0.05
20.12.2025	3.2	3	1.2	0.4	0.05
21.12.2025	7	6	3.7	1.3	0.2
22.12.2025	8.8	7.9	5.5	2.9	0.4
23.12.2025	12.2	10.9	8.5	5.1	1.3
24.12.2025	14.5	13.2	11	8.3	3.3
25.12.2025	16	15	13.2	11.1	5.6
26.12.2025	17.8	17.1	15	14.2	8.5
27.12.2025	20.2	19.3	17	16.6	10.8
28.12.2025	21	19.5	19	18.15	12.8
29.12.2025	21	20.8	19.8	19.5	15
30.12.2025	21.2	20.8	20.5	20	16.9
31.12.2025	22.7	21.2	20.6	20	18.4

GROWTH DATA**FSP**

DATE	1	2	3	4	5
11.12.2025	-	-	-	-	-
12.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
13.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
14.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
15.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
16.12.2025	SG	0	0	0	0
17.12.2025	G	0	0	0	0
18.12.2025	G	0	0	0	0
19.12.2025	2.2	0	0	0	0
20.12.2025	4.3	SG	0	0	0
21.12.2025	7.1	G	0	0	0
22.12.2025	9.8	0.3	0	0	0
23.12.2025	12.7	1.5	0	0	0
24.12.2025	15	3	0	0	0
25.12.2025	17.5	4.6	0	0	0
26.12.2025	18.7	6	0	0	0
27.12.2025	19.2	7.1	0	0	0
28.12.2025	19.2	8.2	0	0	0
29.12.2025	19.2	9.1	0	0	0
30.12.2025	19.2	9.2	0	0	0
31.12.2025	19.2	10.1	0	0	0

GROWTH DATA**BSP**

DATE	1	2	3	4	5
11.12.2025	-	-	-	-	-
12.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
13.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
14.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
15.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
16.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
17.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
18.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
19.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
20.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
21.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
22.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
23.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
24.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
25.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
26.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
27.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
28.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
29.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
30.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0
31.12.2025	0	0	0	0	0

